

LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOR AND COMPETENCE OF SCHOOLHEADS: BASIS FOR PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18933355>

ABSTRACT

This study examined the leadership behaviors and leadership competence of school heads in public elementary schools in the Division of Mabalacat City during the School Year 2023–2024. Using a quantitative-descriptive and correlational research design, the study assessed leadership behaviors in terms of strategic, instructional, managerial, human resource management, cultural, micro-political, and external development leadership, as perceived by 120 teacher-respondents. Leadership competence was likewise evaluated across educational, supervisory, organizing, and administrative domains. Weighted mean and Spearman’s Rho were employed for statistical analysis. Findings revealed that overall leadership behavior was rated “very desirable” (WM = 3.84). Instructional, managerial, human resource, cultural, micro-political, and external development leadership were all rated very desirable, while strategic leadership was assessed as somewhat desirable. In terms of competence, school heads were rated “high” overall (WM = 3.93) across all four domains: educational, supervisory, organizing, and administrative competence. Correlation analysis indicated a statistically significant relationship between leadership behaviors and all areas of leadership competence ($p < 0.05$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This suggests that higher levels of competence are associated with more desirable leadership behaviors. Based on these findings, a professional development program was proposed to strengthen leadership practices and supervisory skills. The study concludes that enhancing school heads’ competencies can further improve leadership effectiveness and recommends the implementation, monitoring, and continuous evaluation of the proposed program.

Keywords: *Leadership behavior, Leadership competence, School heads, Professional development program, Public elementary schools*

INTRODUCTION

All governments around the world are concerned with advancing their educational systems and making them more effective and meaningful. Education provides the basis for the development of the skills of the human capital designed to accomplish the strategic goals. As such, education must be fundamental. Successful schools are the results of competent governance demonstrated by the school heads in collaborative partnerships with relevant stakeholders.

Recent studies further emphasize the importance of leadership competence in ensuring effective school governance and administration. Lareza and Espiritu (2024) examined school principals' leadership competencies and governance practices, finding that principals and teachers rated leadership competence similarly high across strategic, operational, and instructional domains, supporting the notion that leadership competence is crucial for effective school administration. Their study highlights that transparent governance and effective leadership practices are strongly anchored in the competencies demonstrated by school leaders.

According to Medul (2022), education is widely recognized as an indicator of development. One of the basic purposes of education is to produce trained human resource which can overcome development impediments of a given country. To achieve this, there should be a committed workforce in the sector. Employees of leaders with good behavior commit their time, energy and efforts to work which result in high productivity. Similarly, Intud and Fernal (2025) investigated leadership styles and competencies of school heads and found that effective leadership significantly influences school effectiveness and teacher performance, underscoring the importance of leadership behavior and competence in educational outcomes. These findings reinforce the idea that leadership behavior and competence are interrelated constructs essential for improving institutional performance.

The effectiveness of the school system depends to a large extent on those who are in the helm, or those who lead. The educational system will go only as far as where the leaders will take it. If there is desire and willpower, one can become an effective leader. Good leaders develop through a never ending process of self-study, education, training, and experience. Good leaders are continually working and studying to improve their leadership skills; they are not resting on their laurels (Acera and Tan, 2023).

School heads have been traditionally viewed as leaders because of the formal authority vested in their position. Early leadership research attempted to identify which personality traits made a person a leader; the value of using different leadership strategies with people at differing levels of willingness and readiness; the leaders' emphasis on tasks versus relationships; and the extent to which subordinates should be

utilized in the decision-making process. Majority of these theories were based on the traditional view of a leader in relation to his/her followers. In order to expand current understandings of leadership beyond the limiting perspective, it is necessary to challenge the very nature and meaning of the constructs used in defining the subject.

According to Aquino et al. (2021), the school head is the axis around which many elements of the school take precedence. He is responsible for every dimension of the operation of the system, be it academic or administrative. The school head must be inclined to make almost all of the school's decisions. Thus, the school head must be a director, a planner, and a judgment maker. A trustworthy school head would use collaboration as a working technique by establishing teams and smaller units of team members to examine proposals or tactics. It is up to the school head to be a strong team player to impact the quality of instruction.

Leadership is the ability to influence a group toward the achievement of a particular goal. The nature of the Philippine schools is such that the person appointed by higher authority to act as the school manager is at the same time the leader in that school organization. A leader demonstrates his ability in assisting the group in attaining its goals. It is therefore the chief function of leadership to assist in the achievement of goals and the ability of developing and communicating a vision to a group of people that will make the vision true.

Espiritu (2021) asserted that leadership is an elusive ideological capability that must be imbibed by humanity. This gives great responsibility to provide high standard quality of life, determining social function, making firm and efficient decisions. Leaders have the responsibility of developing future visions and motivating organizational members to work toward achieving their visions. They must have the capability to look beyond daily happenings and visualize a brighter future to be effective leaders.

Successful leaders work closely with those they lead, and through this collaboration, they can influence others to pursue common goals and achievements to have quality institutional objectives. Influential leaders are successful at convincing others to follow and pursue a shared mission and vision by establishing trustworthy relationships. An effective school head is one who continuously gives meaningful personal and emotional support to teachers, promotes self-confidence, and holds teachers in high esteem. It is such a relationship that fosters favorable climate to heighten students' morale as well as improve students' achievement, and hence, school performance. This shows how the school head runs the school and manages the teachers is a big responsibility. A lot of pressures and numerous problems may crop up for the school administrator to wrestle day in and day out. It takes effort to effectively remove stumbling blocks to progress the achievement (Dellomas & Deri, 2022).

In the educational system, it is imperative to assess the leadership styles of the school heads, the managers in the schools as this has been proven vital in the pursuit of quality education. School heads are important in the school system because they are the key officials who are responsible for the effectiveness of the organization. Change and

upheaval make it essential for institutions to have anchors and guiding purposes. School heads feel this need.

The school head as the leader in the school system should be effective in his leadership. The quality of leader-member relations is the most important influence on the manager's power and effectiveness. If the manager gets along well with the rest of the group, if group members respect the manager for reasons of personality, character or ability, then the manager may not have to rely on formal rank authority.

The position of the school head requires that he has sound discretion and dexterity of judgment. Many can become head teachers or principals but not everybody can become an effective leader. The position of school administrator is considered a leadership position. Because of this, the person occupying the position should try his best to be a true effective leader.

The school head must have a clear understanding of his functions, a desire for knowledge of group dynamics, is academically and professionally honest; has a desire and readiness to cut red tape, is understanding, patient and imaginative. An effective educational leader should possess or develop a vision as educator. His analysis of problems will certainly provide one kind of a clue about the changes that are needed. He should develop clear, attainable goals and dedicate himself to them; he must have the desire to lead people from all walks of life and demonstrate the willingness to respond to critics after listening with an open mind. As a good and effective instructional leader, he is willing to take risks.

There are numerous approaches in leadership and the effectiveness of such approaches is dependent upon the situations. The research of Liwa (2018) showed that leadership behaviors appropriate in one situation were not necessarily appropriate in another. Nevertheless, despite growing evidence that effective leadership behavior depend at least particularly on the leader's situation, some researchers have reached the conclusion that certain management behaviors are in fact more effective than others in a relatively wide variety of circumstances.

The first aspect of the behavioral approach to leadership shifted the focus from the individual leader to the functions that leaders performed within their groups. In order for a group to operate effectively, someone had to perform two major functions: "task-related" or problem-solving functions and "group maintenance" or social functions. Studies in these areas have found that most effective groups have form of shared leadership in which one person (usually the manager or formal leader) performs the task function, while another group member performs the social functions. Leadership specialization may occur because a given individual has the temperament or skill to play one role.

A manager's choice of leadership style must reckon with such situational forces as the organization's preferred style, the specific work group, the nature of the group's work tasks, the pressures of time, and even environment factors, all of which may affect organization members' attitudes towards authority.

The actions of school leaders impact school capacity and may either enhance or diminish student achievement. The effective educational leader is one who has the ability to develop a school's capacity to enhance student learning through the motivation of teachers, staff and students. Such leadership is determined by the followers, not the leaders (Pricellas, 2016).

Recognizing the value of improving the leadership skills of the school head is closely related to the need for organizations to recruit and retain high-performing teachers. The heart of successful leadership practice includes personal skills (advancement of self-awareness, critical and complex management of stress and well-being and conflict resolution); interpersonal skills (building relationships through constructive communication, gaining authority and strength, promoting productivity, and resolving and reclosing tensions); and group skills (inspiring and empowering others, building successful performance, and leading progressive adjustment) (Villanueva, et.al., 2021).

As the need for school heads with competent and adequate leadership skills become the ultimate phenomenon among schools, school leaders have to be evaluated in order to figure out if they truly embody the type of leaders who can lead and are capable to address the problems faced by the schools, particularly on raising the quality education offered to stakeholders and the same that the society expects from them.

The researcher was challenged to bring this issue to the fore and looked into this aspect particularly in the public elementary schools in the Division of Mabalacat City to assess leadership behavior and competence of the school heads during the school year 2023-2024.

Research Questions

This study determined the leadership behavior and competence of school heads in the public elementary schools in the Division of Mabalacat City during the school year 2023 – 2024.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following sub-questions:

1. What is the leadership behavior of the school heads as assessed by their teachers in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 Strategic leadership;
 - 1.2 Instructional leadership;
 - 1.3 Managerial leadership;
 - 1.4 Human resource management;
 - 1.5 Cultural leadership;
 - 1.6 Micro Political leadership; and
 - 1.7 External development leadership?
2. What is the level of leadership competence of the school heads as assessed by their teachers in terms of the following:
 - 2.1 Educational competence;
 - 2.2 Supervisory competence;

- 2.3 Organizing competence; and
- 2.4 Administrative competence?
- 3. Is there a significant relationship between leadership behavior and leadership competence of the school heads?
- 4. What professional development program may be proposed to enhance the leadership behavior and competence of school heads?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study determined the leadership behaviors and leadership competence of the school heads in the public elementary schools in Division of Mabalacat City during the school year 2023 – 2024 through the quantitative-descriptive research design.

The quantitative-descriptive research design was utilized to determine the leadership behaviors of school heads in terms of strategic leadership, instructional leadership, managerial leadership, human resource management, cultural leadership, micro political leadership, and external development leadership as assessed by their teachers. It was also used to determine the leadership competence of the schools heads in terms of educational competence, supervisory competence, organizing competence, and administrative competence as assessed by their teachers. The study is also correlational as it sought to find out the relationship between the leadership behaviors and the leadership competence of school heads.

Based on the findings, a professional development program was proposed to enhance the leadership behavior and competence of the school heads in the public elementary schools in Division of Mabalacat City.

Sources of Data

There were 120 teachers in the public elementary schools in Division of Mabalacat City who served as respondents of the study. They provided pertinent information to answer the sub-problems raised in the study.

Instrumentation and Data Collection

The main data gathering instrument used in the study was a constructed questionnaire which consists of two parts. Part I determined the leadership behaviors of school heads in terms of strategic leadership, instructional leadership, managerial leadership, human resource management, cultural leadership, micro political leadership, and external development leadership. Part II focused on the leadership competence of school heads in terms of educational competence, supervisory competence, organizing competence; and administrative competence. Upon completion of the questionnaire, it

was presented to the researcher's adviser. Suggestions were incorporated to improve the instrument.

The researcher distributed the questionnaires herself to ensure 100% retrieval. Data gathered were tabulated and interpreted through the use of appropriate statistical tools.

Tools for Data Analysis

To following tools were used to treat the data statistically:

1. Weighted Mean

This was used to answer sub-problem numbers 1 and 2.
The formula is:

$$WM = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$$

Where:

WM = Weighted Mean
 $\sum fx$ = the sum of the products per column
 N = the number of respondents

Data gathered were interpreted by using the following references:

Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)	
		For Sub-problem no. 1	For Sub-problem no. 2
5	4.50 - 5.00	Highly Desirable (HD)	Very High (VH)
4	3.50 - 4.29	Very Desirable (VD)	High (H)
3	2.50 - 3.49	Somewhat Desirable (SD)	Average (A)
2	1.50 - 2.49	Undesirable (U)	Low (L)
1	1.00 - 1.49	Very Undesirable (VU)	Very Low (VL)

2. Spearman's Rho

This was used to answer sub-problem number 3 regarding the significance of the relationship between the leadership behaviors and the leadership competence of the school heads.

RESULTS

Leadership Behavior of the School Heads as Assessed by Teachers

This section presents the leadership behavior of the school heads in the Division of Mabalacat City during the school year 2023-2024 in terms of strategic leadership, instructional leadership, managerial leadership, human resource management, cultural leadership, micro political leadership, and external development leadership to answer sub-problem number 1.

The data are presented in Tables 1A, 1B, 1C, 1D, 1E, 1F, and 1G

Strategic Leadership

Strategic leadership refers to how schools envision and plan their work, clearly articulate goals, implement actions and monitor the impact of school improvement. It is when school heads use their creative problem-solving skills or strategic issues to help team members and the school to achieve long term goals.

Table 1A presents the leadership behavior of the school heads in terms of strategic leadership.

Table 1A
Leadership Behavior of School Heads in
Terms of Strategic Leadership

INDICATORS	WM	DE
The school head ...		
• expects works to be done	1.37	VU
• delegates responsibility	4.34	VD
• assigns duty during planning period	4.30	VD
• over emphasize control	2.70	SD
• is rigid and inflexible	3.30	SD
• assigns too much paper work	3.37	SD
• uses the words <i>I</i> and <i>me</i> too frequently	3.44	SD
Overall WM	3.26	SD
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Desirable (HD)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Desirable (VD)
3	2.50-3.49	Somewhat Desirable (SD)
2	1.50-2.49	Undesirable (U)
1	1.00-1.49	Very Undesirable (VU)

Table 1A shows the assessment of the teachers on their school heads' leadership behavior with respect to strategic leadership. It is evident that the teachers perceived that the school heads have "somewhat desirable" strategic leadership as shown in the overall weighted mean of 3.26. This implies that engaging the entire school staff in making decisions results in more commitment to school reform initiatives.

Effective leaders have many common qualities. Good group leaders make an effort to learn and practice skills so they can listen openly to others, offer and accept constructive suggestions, give clear directions, set and meet deadlines, give formal and informal presentations, help members identify and solve problems, set an example of desired behavior, show appreciation of others' contributions, show understanding, encourage members to exchange ideas, handle conflict, guide the group in goal setting and decision making, delegate responsibilities, ask questions of the group to prompt responses and create a productive atmosphere.

Instructional Leadership

Instructional leadership refers to a model of school leadership in which a school head works alongside teachers to provide support and guidance in establishing best practices in teaching.

Table 1B presents the leadership behavior of school heads in terms of instructional leadership.

Table 1B
Leadership Behavior of School Heads in
Terms of Instructional Leadership

INDICATORS	WM	DE
The school head ...		
• frequently interrupts my teaching	4.30	VD
• demonstrates a lack of wisdom	3.63	VD
• has knowledge about instructional strategies	4.34	VD
• has rules but does not always enforce them	3.30	SD
• helps people accountable	3.70	VD
Overall WM	3.85	VD
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Desirable (HD)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Desirable (VD)
3	2.50-3.49	Somewhat Desirable (SD)
2	1.50-2.49	Undesirable (U)
1	1.00-1.49	Very Undesirable (VU)

Table 1B presents the assessment of the teachers on their school heads' leadership behavior with respect to instructional leadership. Table 1B shows that the

teachers perceived that their school heads had “very desirable” strategic leadership as suggested by the overall weighted mean of 3.85.

The duties of the school head to monitor instruction increased along with their responsibility to help teachers improve their teaching. With this change in responsibilities, school heads discovered the need to effectively evaluate instruction and assist teachers as they work to improve their instructional technique. Teachers share responsibility for staff development, curriculum development and instructional supervision with the school head, who serve as a leader of leaders rather than the sole leader in the school.

Managerial Leadership

Managerial leadership refers to the ability of people in managerial positions in their institutions to influence and lead the teachers.

Table 1C presents the leadership behavior of the school heads in terms of managerial leadership.

Table 1C
Leadership Behavior of School Heads in
Terms of Managerial Leadership

INDICATORS	WM	DE
The school head ...		
• is able to keep confidence	4.30	VD
• is afraid to question his/her superior	3.41	SD
• passes the buck rather than dealing with a situation	3.70	VD
• has double standard	2.66	SD
• is partial to influential parent	3.63	VD
• shows favoritism to some teachers	4.34	VD
• supports me even if I am wrong	3.59	VD
Overall WM	3.66	VD
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Desirable (HD)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Desirable (VD)
3	2.50-3.49	Somewhat Desirable (SD)
2	1.50-2.49	Undesirable (U)
1	1.00-1.49	Very Undesirable (VU)

Table 1C presents the assessment of the teachers on the school heads’ leadership behavior with respect to managerial leadership. It is evident that the teachers perceived that the school heads have “very desirable” strategic leadership as suggested by the overall weighted mean of 3.66.

The duties of the school head to monitor instruction increased along with their responsibility to help teachers improve their teaching. With this change in responsibilities, school heads discovered the need to effectively evaluate instruction and assist teachers as they work to improve their instructional technique, creates a vision and confidence that there are so insurmountable obstacles to dreams, wishes and potentials; and advocates for their rights and needs the value of a nurturing relationship between school head and teacher is explored. The school heads strongly encourages the teacher to identify and try new things that they feel might be beneficial to the learners.

Human Resources Management

Human resource management refers to the strategic and coherent approach to the effective and efficient management of people in an institution.

Table 1D presents the leadership behavior of the school heads in terms of human resource management.

Table 1D
Leadership Behavior of School Heads in
Terms of Human Resources
Management

INDICATORS	WM	DE
The school head ...		
• calls me by name	3.66	VD
• uses eye contact	4.34	VD
• demonstrates caring attitude	4.30	VD
• involves me in decision making	3.56	VD
• does not listen	3.63	VD
• models good communication skills	4.41	VD
• provides positive reinforcement	3.70	VD
Overall WM	3.94	VD
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Desirable (HD)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Desirable (VD)
3	2.50-3.49	Somewhat Desirable (SD)
2	1.50-2.49	Undesirable (U)
1	1.00-1.49	Very Undesirable (VU)

Table 1D presents the assessment of the teachers on the school heads' leadership behavior with respect to human resource management. It is evident that the teachers perceived that the school heads have "very desirable" human resource management as suggested by the overall weighted mean of 3.94.

Utilizing a socio-linguistic approach has classified the desire for smooth interpersonal relations as a dominant value of Philippine society. It is defined as facility at getting along with others in such a way as to avoid outward signs of conflicts; gloom or sour look, harsh words, open disagreement, or physical violence.

Leadership at work in education institution is thus a dynamic process where an individual is not only responsible for the group’s task, but also actively seeks the collaboration and commitment of all the group members in achieving group goals in a particular context. Leadership development and training has focused primarily on equipping individuals with skills to manage their external environment – skills such as effective communication, team building, decision-making, negotiation and conflict management. These are important leadership skills.

Cultural Leadership

Cultural leadership refers to the ability to drive culture and values to influence stakeholders and communities to create a positive, inclusive and engaging working environment.

Table 1E presents the leadership behavior of the school heads in terms of cultural leadership.

Table 1E
Leadership Behavior of School Heads in
Terms of Cultural Leadership

INDICATORS	WM	DE
The school head ...		
• promotes cooperation among staff	3.66	VD
• respects the culture of the learners	4.34	VD
• promotes gender equality	4.41	VD
• promotes culture stability	4.37	VD
• promotes sense of well-being	4.30	VD
• develops an understanding of purpose	3.70	VD
• develops a shared vision of what the school could be like on a short evaluation	3.63	VD
Overall WM	4.06	VD
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Desirable (HD)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Desirable (VD)
3	2.50-3.49	Somewhat Desirable (SD)
2	1.50-2.49	Undesirable (U)
1	1.00-1.49	Very Undesirable (VU)

Table 1E presents the assessment of the teachers on the school heads' leadership behavior in terms of cultural leadership. This shows that the teachers perceived that the school heads have "very desirable" cultural leadership as suggested by the overall weighted mean of 4.06.

The school heads are also responsible for facilitating their school's interactions with parents and others in the school community. This responsibility includes working with the parents when disciplinary issues arise, when learners are not succeeding academically, and when parents have concerns. School heads also interact with parents who serve on school advisory boards and parent / teacher organizations.

Micro-Political Leadership

In micro-political leadership, the school head develops systems and relationships to leverage staff expertise and influence in order to influence the school's identity, culture and performance.

Table 1F presents the leadership behavior of the school heads in terms of micro-political leadership.

Table 1F
Leadership Behavior of School Heads in
Terms of Micro-Political Leadership

INDICATORS	WM	DE
The school head ...		
• provides and enforces clear structure, rules and procedure	4.30	VD
• establishes routines regarding the running of the school that staff understand and follow	3.70	VD
• uses Self-Evaluation Form in a very good way	4.34	VD
• has a lenient relationship with the LGU officials	4.37	VD
• is transparent about MOOE	3.63	VD
• lets staff members know what is expected to them	3.66	VD
Overall WM	4.00	VD
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Desirable (HD)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Desirable (VD)
3	2.50-3.49	Somewhat Desirable (SD)
2	1.50-2.49	Undesirable (U)
1	1.00-1.49	Very Undesirable (VU)

Table 1F presents the assessment of the teachers on the school heads' behavior with respect to micro-political leadership. It is evident that the teachers perceived that the

school heads have “very desirable” micro-political leadership as suggested by the overall weighted mean of 4.00.

The role of the school heads of providing public relations for the school is a primary function of the position. It does no good to do great things and keep this to oneself. Every opportunity opens the doors to visitors, and one must have the story of his success whenever he can.

External Development Leadership

In external development leadership, the school head will design structures and processes that result in community engagement, support and ownership.

Table 1G presents the leadership behavior of the school heads in terms of external development leadership.

Table 1G
Leadership Behavior of School Heads in
Terms of External Development
Leadership

INDICATORS	WM	DE
The school head ...		
• has a good relationship with the parents	4.41	VD
• has lenient relationship with the barangay officials	4.34	VD
• is charismatic in learners’ welfare	3.70	VD
• has a good impression with the community	4.30	VD
• establishes a set of standard operating procedure	4.37	VD
• provides opportunity input on all important decision with the community	3.66	VD
Overall WM	4.13	VD
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Desirable (HD)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Desirable (VD)
3	2.50-3.49	Somewhat Desirable (SD)
2	1.50-2.49	Undesirable (U)
1	1.00-1.49	Very Undesirable (VU)

Table 1G presents the assessment of the teachers on the school heads’ leadership behavior with respect to external development leadership. It is evident that the teachers rate their school heads to have “very desirable” external development leadership as suggested by the overall weighted mean of 4.13. The teachers consider their school heads to provide opportunity input on all important decision with the community and have a good relationship with the parents as well. Aside from the school heads’ major roles,

they have more in store for them to perform which brings the school head closer to parents and students.

Summary Table

Indicators	WM	DE
• Strategic leadership	3.26	SD
• Instructional leadership	3.85	VD
• Managerial leadership	3.66	VD
• Human resources management	3.94	VD
• Cultural leadership	4.06	VD
• Micro-political leadership	4.00	VD
• External development leadership	4.13	VD
Overall WM	3.84	VD

The Summary Table summarizes the aforementioned leadership behaviors of the school heads as perceived by the teachers. For the teachers, their school heads' external development leadership is the most desirable behavior they have with overall weighted mean of 4.13, while their strategic leadership is the least desirable with overall weighted mean of 3.26. The study shows that school heads should improve their strategic leadership and continue to use their external development leadership to make the school a better place for learning.

The characteristics of the school heads often determine the dynamics of school community and the economic outcomes of school policies and procedures. When a school lacks effective leadership, minimal learning takes place. School leaders, beginning with the school head, must provide strong leadership that sets a tone for daily operations of the school community. In the absence of such leadership, discipline breaks down, academic falter, and a sense of organized chaos reigns. School leadership is about dynamic modeling that encourages collegiality and promotes excellence in every aspect of the school community.

Level of Leadership Competence of School Heads

This section presents the level of leadership competence of the school heads in terms of educational competence, supervisory competence, organizing competence, and administrative competence as perceived by the teachers to answer sub-problem number 2. The data are presented in Tables 2A, 2B, 2C, and 2D

Educational Competence

Educational competence is the ability to effectively apply skills, knowledge and attitudes in a real-world work environment.

Table 2A presents the data.

Table 2A
Leadership Competence of School Heads
in Terms of Educational Competence

INDICATORS	WM	DE
1. Setting instructional goals	4.13	H
2. Designing instructional units	3.98	H
3. Developing and adapting curricula	4.03	H
4. Evaluating and selecting learning resources	4.16	H
5. Evaluating the utilization of learning resources	3.87	H
6. Producing learning materials	3.94	H
7. Supervision in clerical model	3.90	H
8. Planning for individual	3.90	H
Overall WM	3.99	H
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Very High (VH)
4	3.50-4.49	High (H)
3	2.50-3.49	Average (A)
2	1.50-2.49	Low (L)
1	1.00-1.49	Very Low (VL)

Table 2A clearly shows that school heads are highly competent in terms of educational competency with an overall weighted mean of 3.99. This implies that the school heads are very much capable of their high competency level.

It can be noted that in terms of educational competence, school heads have high competence in performing tasks like setting instructional goals, designing instructional units, developing and adapting curricula, evaluating and selecting learning resources and their utilization, producing learning materials, supervising clerical models, and planning for individual with weighted means that ranged from 3.87 to 4.16.

School heads must lead their school through goal-setting process in which learner achievement data is analyzed, improvement areas are identified and actions for change are initiated. This process involves working collaboratively with staff and school

community to identify discrepancies between current and desired outcomes, to set and prioritize goals to help close the gap, to develop improvement and monitoring strategies aimed at accomplishing the goals, and to communicate goals and change efforts to the entire school community. School heads must also ensure that staff development needs are identified in alignment with school improvement priorities and that these needs are addressed with appropriate professional learning opportunities.

Supervisory Competence

Supervisory competence is focused around the five foundation areas of theories, roles and modalities.

Table 2B presents the data.

Table 2B
Leadership Competence of School Heads
in Terms of Supervisory Competence

INDICATORS	WM	DE
1. Building a healthy climate	3.77	H
2. Team building	3.66	H
3. Resolving conflict	3.70	H
4. Making decisions	3.84	H
5. Planning and organizing meetings	3.88	H
6. Recruiting and selecting personnel	3.85	H
7. Assigning personnel	3.92	H
8. Bringing about change	3.91	H
Overall WM	3.82	H
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Very High (VH)
4	3.50-4.49	High (H)
3	2.50-3.49	Average (A)
2	1.50-2.49	Low (L)
1	1.00-1.49	Very Low (VL)

In terms of supervisory competence exhibited by the school head, the overall weighted mean is 3.82 described as highly competent as shown in Table 2B. The study reveals that the school heads are highly knowledgeable in line with supervisory functions.

School administrators promote vision, mission and goals and develop a means to reach them. They ensure quality of instruction, model teaching practice, supervise curriculum, and ensure quality of teaching resources. They oversee the operations of the school, recruit, hire, fire, induct, and mentor teachers and administrators; develop leadership capacity and professional development opportunities and represent the school

in the community, develop capital, tend to public relations, recruit learners, buffer and mediate external interests, and advocate for the school's interests.

Organizing Competence

Organizing competence is the total of the skills, attitudes and learning of organization needs to perform its tasks.

Table 2C presents the data.

Table 2C
Leadership Competence of School Heads
in Terms of Organizing Competence

INDICATORS	WM	DE
1. Revising existing structures	3.90	H
2. Assimilating programs	3.92	H
3. Monitoring new arrangements	3.87	H
4. Developing a staffing plan	3.84	H
5. Informing the public	3.92	H
6. Student discipline	3.98	H
7. Policies and procedures	3.94	H
Overall WM	3.91	H
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Very High (VH)
4	3.50-4.49	High (H)
3	2.50-3.49	Average (A)
2	1.50-2.49	Low (L)
1	1.00-1.49	Very Low (VL)

The level of competency of the school heads on organization competence as revealed in the study with the overall weighted mean of 3.91 which indicates that the school heads are very much skillful and expert in student discipline. The study recognizes that in large multidisciplinary schools it is not always possible for a school head to have a detailed knowledge of the work of every staff member.

It could be gleaned from the data that the school heads perform their role in organizational matters with utmost and high performance. School heads are supposed to interact with teachers, parents, community members, and pupils. Strong collaboration and instructional skills have replaced strong bureaucratic skills as important attributes of effective school head. School heads need continuous professional development opportunities to support their efforts toward school improvement and revitalize their commitment to creating and sustaining positive learning communities.

Effective school heads are accessible to every teacher and pupil, acting as a sounding board for both ideas and emotions. School heads can continuously take stock of the school culture and use feedback to make reform efforts more effective.

Administrative Competence

Administrative competence refers to the skills, knowledge, qualifications, capacity or authority to manage or direct the affairs of an institution.

Table 2D presents the data.

Table 2D
Leadership Competence of School Heads
in Terms of Administrative Competence

INDICATORS	WM	DE
1. Able to employ managerial planning tools	3.94	H
2. Organize, supervise and manage financial affairs of the school	3.90	H
3. Familiar with the budgetary needs of the school such as operation and maintenance costs.	3.98	H
4. Awareness of the learner profile as to enrolment promotion, drop-out and repeaters.	4.13	H
5. Plans for the facilities and equipment of the school.	3.92	H
6. Apply rational decision-making models and procedures in the administration of department programs.	3.94	H
7. Able to keep accurate records of purchasing needs, inventories, expenditure and other business functions.	4.16	H
Overall WM	4.00	H
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Very High (VH)
4	3.50-4.49	High (H)
3	2.50-3.49	Average (A)
2	1.50-2.49	Low (L)
1	1.00-1.49	Very Low (VL)

The administrative competence of the school heads as assessed by the teachers is presented in Table 2D where the teachers rated their school heads as highly competent with respect to educational aspect as reckoned by the overall weighted mean of 4.00. The study shows that the school heads are knowledgeable about their duties and responsibilities of being an administrator. This finding implies that the primary duty of a school head is to manage the well-being and ongoing development of staff in the school.

The school head is expected to: Advise staff on planning for and preferred timing of their application for promotion as an integral part of the regular performance management review; Identify any possible conflicts of interest between the school head and the staff member such as different approaches to research / theory; and Provide guidance and counseling to the staff member.

Summary Table

Indicators	WM	DE
• Educational competence	3.99	H
• Supervisory competence	3.82	H
• Organizing competence	3.91	H
• Administrative competence	4.00	H
Overall WM	3.93	H

The Summary Table summarizes the aforementioned leadership competence of the school heads. As perceived by the teachers, the leadership competence of the school heads had an overall weighted mean of 3.93 with a descriptive rating of “High.” This finding may be an indication that there is still more room for improvement on the leadership competence of the school heads.

For effectiveness in leadership, competency represents an attempt to capture the experience, lessons learned and knowledge of experienced leaders to provide a guiding framework for the benefit of others and organizations. Thus, leaders need to improve on competencies in organizations to survive and continue to nurture. These competencies include such skills as leadership styles, effective communication, convincing others and professionalism.

Relationship Between Leadership Behavior and Leadership Competence of the School Heads

This section presents the relationship between leadership behavior and leadership competence of the school heads to answer sub-problem number 3.

The data are presented in Table 3A (leadership behavior vs. educational competence); Table 3B (leadership behavior vs. supervisory competence); Table 3C (leadership behavior vs. organizing competence); and Table 3D (leadership behavior vs. administrative competence).

Table 3A
Relationship Between Leadership Behavior and Educational Competence of School Heads

Indicators	r-value	Descriptive Equivalent	p-value
Strategic Leadership and Educational Competence	0.56	Moderate correlation	< .00001*
Instructional Leadership and Educational Competence	0.78	High Correlation	< .00001*
Managerial Leadership and Educational Competence	0.67	Moderate Correlation	< .00001*
Human Resource Management and Educational Competence	0.62	Moderate Correlation	< .00001*
Cultural Leadership and Educational Competence	0.43	Low Correlation	< .00001*
Micro Political Leadership and Educational Competence	0.71	High Correlation	< .00001*
External Development Leadership and Educational Competence	0.51	Moderate correlation	< .00001*

**significant at the .05 level*

With p-values less than 0.05 level of significance, there is a significant relationship between leadership behavior and educational competence of school heads. This could mean that as the school heads' leadership behavior becomes highly desirable, the educational competence also becomes high.

Table 3B
Relationship Between Leadership Behavior and Supervisory Competence of School Heads

Indicators	r-value	Descriptive Equivalent	p-value
Strategic Leadership and Supervisory Competence	0.63	Moderate correlation	< .00001*

Instructional Leadership and Supervisory Competence	0.44	Low Correlation	< .00001*
Managerial Leadership and Supervisory Competence	0.81	High correlation	< .00001*
Human Resource Management and Supervisory Competence	0.78	High correlation	< .00001*
Cultural Leadership and Supervisory Competence	0.39	Low correlation	.000072*
Micro Political Leadership and Supervisory Competence	0.70	Moderate Correlation	< .00001*
External Development Leadership and Supervisory Competence	0.48	Low correlation	< .00001*

**significant at the .05 level*

With p-values less than 0.05 level of significance, there is a significant relationship between leadership behavior and supervisory competence of school heads. This could mean that as the school heads' leadership behavior becomes highly desirable, the school heads also become highly competent in terms of supervision.

Table 3C
Relationship Between Leadership Behavior and Organizing Competence of School Heads

Indicators	r-value	Descriptive Equivalent	p-value
Strategic Leadership and Organizing Competence	0.83	High correlation	< .00001*
Instructional Leadership and Organizing Competence	0.48	Low Correlation	< .00001*
Managerial Leadership and Organizing Competence	0.77	High correlation	< .00001*
Human Resource Management and Organizing Competence	0.82	High correlation	< .00001*

Cultural Leadership and Organizing Competence	0.38	Low correlation	.000114*
Micro Political Leadership and Organizing Competence	0.56	Moderate Correlation	< .00001*
External Development Leadership and Organizing Competence	0.51	Moderate correlation	< .00001*

**significant at the .05 level*

With p-values less than 0.05 level of significance, there is a significant relationship between leadership behavior and organizing competence of school heads. This could mean that as the school heads' leadership behavior becomes highly desirable, the school heads also become highly competent in terms of organizing functions, programs, policies, and procedures.

Table 3D
Relationship Between Leadership Behavior and Administrative Competence of School Heads

Indicators	r-value	Descriptive Equivalent	p-value
Strategic Leadership and Administrative Competence	0.56	Moderate Correlation	< .00001*
Instructional Leadership and Administrative Competence	0.41	Low Correlation	.000028*
Managerial Leadership and Administrative Competence	0.83	High Correlation	< .00001*
Human Resource Management and Administrative Competence	0.71	High Correlation	< .00001*
Cultural Leadership and Administrative Competence	0.46	Low correlation	< .00001*
Micro Political Leadership and Administrative Competence	0.82	High Correlation	< .00001*
External Development Leadership and Administrative Competence	0.64	Moderate correlation	< .00001*

**significant at the .05 level*

With p-values less than 0.05 level of significance, there is a significant relationship between leadership behavior and administrative competence of school heads. This could mean that as the school heads' leadership behavior becomes highly desirable, they also become highly competent in terms of administrative competence.

Proposed Professional Development Program

This section presents the proposed professional development program to enhance the leadership performance and competence of school heads to answer sub-problem number 4.

The proposed professional development program was concerned on the need for improving the school heads' use of appropriate leadership styles in certain supervisory activities and the need for improving the school heads' supervisory skills for a better effect on their teachers and consequently more effective instruction.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The extent of leadership behavior manifested by the school heads as perceived by the teachers is very desirable.
2. The level of competence of the school heads is high as perceived by the teachers.
3. There is significant relationship between the leadership behavior and competence of the school heads as perceived by the teachers. This indicates that the level of competence of the school heads affects their leadership behavior.
4. The proposed professional development program focused on the needs of the school heads for improving their use of appropriate leadership styles and improving their supervisory skills.

Recommendations

On the basis on the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations were offered:

1. The proposed development program should be considered by school officials like the Education Supervisors, District Supervisors and Principal for approval and implementation.
2. The proposed development program should be disseminated through a forum or conference in the District.
3. After the initial implementation, there should be regular and continuous monitoring and evaluation of the proposed development program for further enhancement.

4. To improve the professionalism of the public elementary school heads and ultimately their leadership performance, the proposed development program should be considered for implementation so that mechanisms can be put in place for their implementation.
5. There should be a continuous evaluation of the leadership qualities of the school heads for an effective implementation of RA No. 9155.
6. Although most of the school heads are academically qualified, they may still continue to pursue higher studies in the Graduate Studies to equip them with advanced and more adequate knowledge, skills and competence to be able to perform their tasks inherent to their positions.
7. School authorities concerned may consider sending school heads to seminars and trainings in international levels in which they were found to be deficient.
8. Other researchers may conduct a similar study on a wider scope to validate the findings of the study.

Professional Development Program

Areas of Concern	Goals/Objectives	Strategies/Activities	Expected Outcomes
1. Need for improving the school heads' use of appropriate leadership styles in certain supervisory activities	To improve the leadership styles of school heads as a tool for growth in instructional supervision	In-service education through: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - District LAC session for school heads - Whole group and small study group discussion sessions - Practicum/peer demonstration/ simulations on the applications of leadership styles in the performance of certain supervisory activities - Seminar-workshop on values enhancement relative to ethics on leadership and instructional supervision 	Enhanced knowledge in leadership styles and level of maturity of subordinates Skilled in using appropriate leadership styles Developed values needed for a committed leadership
2. Need for improving the	To improve the school heads'	In-service education on:	Knowledge of the different

<p>school heads' supervisory skills for a better effect on their teachers and consequently more effective instruction</p>	<p>supervisory skills for a better effect on teachers and more effective instruction</p> <p>To enrich the school heads' knowledge, skills and attitudes along leadership styles and instructional supervision</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understanding of child nature - Understanding of human resources - Understanding of educational values - Recognition and diagnosis of teaching difficulties - Techniques for solving leading problem - Improvement in techniques of classroom instruction - Use of materials and equipment - Management of routine matters - Teacher participation - Voluntary request for supervisory assistance <p>Subsidiary activities for the enhancement of leadership skills</p> <p>Inter-school visitation among school heads</p> <p>Field trips to school of school heads awarded recognition as effective school heads</p> <p>Membership in professional organizations</p> <p>Encourage capable school heads to share their knowledge,</p>	<p>supervisory activities</p> <p>Capability in identifying problem areas</p> <p>Skill in identifying teacher growth needs</p> <p>A well-designed individualized supervisory program</p> <p>Broader professional knowledge on management/ leadership/ supervision</p> <p>Articles for professional growth</p> <p>Shared knowledge and contributions of research</p>
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<p>3.School heads' leadership practices</p>	<p>To establish effective functional teams</p>	<p>experiences relative to leadership and supervision by writing and having their articles published in educational magazines</p> <p>Encourage school heads to engage in research focused on the improvement of instruction</p> <p>Giving awards/incentives to school heads with effective schools</p> <p>Grant of government/ foreign scholarship grants to deserving school heads</p> <p>Group participation in making decisions like involving Master Teachers, Head Teachers and the Grade Level Chairman</p> <p>Innovation and promotion of continuous improvement for the school</p> <p>Provision for a clear and motivational mission anchored to DepEd mission and vision to achieve its goal</p>	<p>Highly motivated school heads</p> <p>Highly motivated and knowledgeable school heads</p> <p>Development of strong and harmonious relationship among and with subordinates</p>
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study strictly abided by the ethical considerations in conducting educational research. Before the actual conduct of the study, the Schools Division Office in Mabalacat City and the school heads of the participating public elementary schools were consulted and informed of the purpose and importance of the study. Moreover, the respondents from the 120 teacher-participants were not forced to participate in the study, and their information was given on the purpose and importance of the study to the respondents, and their right to decline and withdraw from the study at any given time without any consequence to their person was assured. Moreover, the study strictly maintained the confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents, as no information on the respondents was solicited and the information gathered was strictly for academic and research purposes only. Moreover, the study assured the respondents that no harm would come to them as the results of the study were not in any way linked to the respondents and the schools involved in the study, and the results of the study were reported objectively and honestly without the intent to misrepresent the results of the study.

Acknowledgments

The researcher extends sincere gratitude to all individuals who provided encouragement and assistance throughout the conduct of the study and the completion of the thesis.

Foremost, profound appreciation is given to Dr. Lailani M. Junio, who served as the thesis adviser, for her invaluable guidance, expertise, and unwavering support. Her insightful comments and constructive feedback significantly contributed to the improvement and completion of this research.

The researcher also expresses heartfelt thanks to the members of the thesis committee, Dr. Joel S. Guileb and Dr. Maria Soledad P. Macale, for their time, thoughtful evaluation, and meaningful suggestions that strengthened the study.

Deep appreciation is likewise extended to Dr. Ricky D. Junio for his assistance and contributions that helped make this research possible.

Special recognition is given to the researcher's parents and partner, Mr. Reniel P. Razon, whose constant encouragement, trust, and moral support sustained the researcher's motivation and optimism throughout the process.

Above all, the researcher offers gratitude to the Almighty God for granting strength, wisdom, and perseverance in accomplishing this academic endeavor.

The researcher sincerely appreciates everyone who became part of this educational journey.

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